

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

Andrew Harding

Centre for Asian Legal Studies
National University of Singapore

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University
Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Malaysia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

National University of Singapore: Andrew Harding
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Sadie Teper/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Malaysia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Malaysia: An Introduction	9
2.2. <i>Planning, Housing Development, and the Ethnic-Preference System</i>	11
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Malaysia: An Introduction	15
3.2. <i>Urban Cleansing and Privatisation</i>	21
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Malaysia: An Introduction	25
4.2. <i>Iskandar Development Region</i>	27
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Malaysia: An Introduction.....	31
5.2. <i>The SPICE Controversy</i>	35
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Malaysia: An Introduction	39
6.2. <i>Public Consultation in the Drafting of Structure/Local Plans</i>	46

Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.2. Planning, Housing Development, and the Ethnic-Preference System

Andrew Harding, *Centre for Asian Legal Studies, National University of Singapore*

Relevance of the Practice

As has been discussed above, ethnic differences are a driver of much policy in Malaysia. From 1971 Malaysia implemented an ethnic-preference policy in favour of the economically disadvantaged majority Malay and also Sabah-Sarawak native (indigenous) population, commonly referred to as *bumiputera* (sons of the soil). This policy was designed to redistribute wealth and opportunity to these communities.²³ Part of the policy was to ensure adequate housing for *bumiputera* citizens, and accordingly it became usual for new housing developments to offer discounts to *bumiputera* purchasers. It is expected that *bumiputera* citizens will generally support Malay parties, especially and traditionally the United Malays National Organisation (UMNO) in elections, on the basis of their delivery of redistributive policies.

Description of the Practice

The legal basis for this policy of affirmative action is as follows. Article 153 of the Constitution, as amended in 1971, allows as an exception to the principle of equality before the law (Article 8) in the form of quota systems in favour of *bumiputera* citizens in various areas (scholarships, trade licences, university admission and public service positions). These do not, however, include housing opportunities as such. Nonetheless there is a strong policy favouring provision of modern, low-cost public housing for the poor, especially poor *bumiputera*. While such housing projects, normally initiated by state governments, which control land issues, are designed to benefit poor citizens, a system of discounts operates also at the middle-class socio-economic level. These discounts involve the cooperation of local authorities, who are empowered under planning and land laws to impose conditions on housing developers as part

²³ Terence Gomez and Johan Saravanamuttu (eds), *The New Economic Policy in Malaysia: Affirmative Action, Ethnic Inequalities, and Social Justice* (NUS Press 2013); Lee Hwok-Aun, 'Affirmative Action: Hefty Action, Mixed Outcomes, Muddled Thinking' in Meredith Weiss (ed), *The Routledge Handbook of Contemporary Malaysia* (Routledge 2016); Andrew Harding, 'Constitutional Trajectory in Malaysia: Constitutionalism without Consensus?' in Michael Dowdle and Michael Wilkinson (eds), *Constitutionalism Beyond Liberalism* (Cambridge University Press 2017); Lee Hwok-Aun, *Affirmative Action in Malaysia and South Africa: Preference for Parity* (Routledge 2021); Andrew Harding, *The Constitution of Malaysia: A Contextual Analysis* (2nd edn, Hart/Bloomsbury, forthcoming 2022) Chapter 3.

of the approval-granting process for development, or land alienation, as the case may be.²⁴ Such conditions are within the broad discretion granted to local planning authorities in handing development control, and normally include a requirement to reserve a number of lots for *bumiputera* purchasers at a discount. These conditions typically involve a 30 per cent *bumiputera* quota (the quota varies somewhat between 20 per cent and 40 per cent, depending on the state) in all housing developments, with developers also being required to give discounts of between 5 per cent and 15 per cent to *bumiputera* applicants. The quota system also applies to commercial units.²⁵ Apart from this there are Malay Reservation Lands, which have a constitutional basis and involve all property built on designated Malay Reservations being allocated to Malays only.²⁶ This latter policy applies in rural areas, whereas new developments are in newly built-up suburban or 'red-earth' suburban or formerly rural areas.

Assessment of the Practice

There have been calls for the planning impositions to be reviewed, particularly in the case of high-end properties where there seems to be no rationale for granting such discounts.²⁷ The ethnic-preference policy seems somewhat irrelevant in an urban middle-class environment, given that for the last 50 years, *bumiputera* citizens have had privileged access to educational, public service, and business opportunities. The continuance or modification of this system is nonetheless a large and sensitive political issue, on which many votes depend, and despite increasing discussion of the ethnic-preference policy in public fora, it seems unlikely there will be major changes in the foreseeable future.²⁸ For present purposes, the impact of these policies and the strong trajectory of Malaysian development is to convert many rural areas into suburban areas, bringing more residents under the control of urban local authorities. This has the unfortunate effect of reducing the resource base of district councils, as we have seen, thus depriving of facilities those very rural areas where most poor *bumiputera* citizens live.

²⁴ Town and Country Planning Act 1976 (TCPA), Sec 22(3); National Land Code, Sec 120.

²⁵ See 'REHDA Institute's State Guidelines on Bumiputra Quotas' (*loanstreet*, undated) <<http://static.loanstreet.com.my.s3.amazonaws.com/assets/bumi-status.jpg>> accessed 16 June 2021.

²⁶ Basharan Begum Mobarak Ali, 'Red Ink Grant: Tracing Legitimacy in History' (2007) 34 *Journal of Malaysian and Comparative Law* 159.

²⁷ Lim Teck Ghee, 'Time to Do away with Housing Quotas' (*Malaysiakini*, 30 October 2007) <<http://www.malaysiakini.com/letters/74176>> ; Fauwaz Abdul Aziz, 'Housing Industry: Bumi Quota a Pressing Issue' (*Malaysiakini*, 30 October 2007) <<http://www.malaysiakini.com/news/74138>>.

²⁸ See Hwok-Aun, 'Affirmative Action', above.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Terence Gomez and Johan Saravanamuttu (eds), *The New Economic Policy in Malaysia: Affirmative Action, Ethnic Inequalities, and Social Justice* (NUS Press 2013)

Lee Hwok-Aun, 'Affirmative Action: Hefty Action, Mixed Outcomes, Muddled Thinking' in Meredith Weiss (ed), *The Routledge Handbook of Contemporary Malaysia* (Routledge 2016)

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

